

Comparative Analysis of Selected Agricultural Sector Performance Indicators between Developed and Developing Nations in Relation to Food Security

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Abstract

A sound agricultural performance may be of help in contributing positively to the food security of many nations, even though, achieving food security in its entirety will continue to be a challenge not only to the emerging nations but also for all countries. In other words, food security issue is not limited to a particular region; it is a challenge that the whole world must proffer a sustainable solution.

Data used in this study were sourced primarily from the database of the United Nation's Food and Agriculture Organization (FAOSTAT) and World Bank. Representative countries were selected from each region of the world for this study. Percentage of the average annual rate of growth was calculated, and aggregated agricultural sector performance indicators of these regions were presented in charts and tables. The result revealed that Africa region recorded low index values for most of the performance indicators. Asia and North America regions are doing much better as they showed significant improvement since the year 2010 as their agricultural contribution to their region's GDP improved. The relationship between the BRIC nations seems not to have a much significant effect on the performance of their agricultural sector. Targeted efforts in Africa, especially, and other regions will result in the overall success of the globe in facilitating sustainable food security.

Keywords: Agriculture; performance; food-security; economy; indicators; sector.

Introduction

The term 'developing nation' could refer to a country that is poor and whose citizens are mostly agricultural workers but that wants to become more advanced socially, culturally and also economically. In other words, a developing nation is a non-industrialized poor country that is seeking to develop its resources and infrastructures through industrialization (thefreedictionary.com, 2014). Recently, according to Wikipedia, developing nations have also been defined as countries that score medium or low in the United Nation's Human Development Index (HDI). On the other hand, a 'developed nation' is a sovereign state that has a highly developed economy, advanced technology, and high standard infrastructure relative to other less industrialized nations. In the general sense, the criteria for determining the level of economic development are gross domestic product (GDP), per capita income, level of industrialization, amount of widespread infrastructure and the general standard of living of the citizens.

There is also need for us to have little understanding from the literature on the actual meaning of food security and food insecurity as it is generally used and accepted by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of United Nations. This is imperative because a country or region with a sound agricultural performance is likely to attain food security. A perspective of food insecurity will help in appreciating the term 'Food Security.'

Food Insecurity and Food Security

Food insecurity occurs when people do not have enough access to food to quench hunger, have an insufficient and limited diet, are anxious about having enough food or need to resort to makeshift or different coping strategies such as begging, scavenging, or relying on emergency assistance programmes or social security programmes in order to keep body and spirit together. (Cook and Frank, 2008). It is worth noting that not

everyone who is food insecure is hungry; people may have enough food to feel satisfied, but have a diet with inadequate levels of essential micronutrients (vitamins and minerals), dietary fiber, vegetables and fruit (Rychetnik *et al.*, 2003). The relationship between food insecurity and poor health status is well documented (Cook and Frank, *ibid*; Hampton, 2007). Food insecurity influences child poor health and development through its effect on nutrition and because of the additional stress it creates on families (Cook and Frank, *ibid*). It affects all aspects of physical, mental, and psychosocial health and is a key factor in low birth weight, stunted growth, being underweight for age or height, chronic poor health, frequent visits or admissions to hospital, and poor cognitive development (Cook and Frank, *ibid*; Kristjansson *et al.*, 2007).

It is documented that in developed nations, the risk of obesity is about 20-40% higher in people who experience food insecurity as compared with the rest of the population. Obesity, in turn, is associated with chronic diseases like diabetes, cardiovascular disease, some cancers, and overall poor health status. Women who are food insecure are particularly mostly affected (Burns, 2004). Several reasons had been found responsible for food insecurity and poor health status. Some of which are:

- a. Extreme cheap foods: these are energy dense, high in fat and sugar and maybe highly palatable. People with limited resources will most likely select foods that are more energy dense so as to satisfy energy needs. In short, it is very cheap to become obese (Burns, 2004; Rush and Rusk, 2009; Te Hotu Manawa Maori, 2008).
- b. Episodic food shortages: this may result in a variety of cognitive, emotional and behavioral changes such as feast or famine cycles and pre-occupation with food and eating related to benefit payment cycles (Burns, 2004).
- c. Distance and transport factors: low socioeconomic areas seem to have fewer readily available sources of healthy food and more fast food outlets. In many countries, health problems related to dietary excess are an ever-increasing threat. In fact, malnutrition and foodborne diarrhea have become a double burden. (Daniel *et al.*, 2009; Rush and Rusk, 2009; Te Hotu Manawa Maori, 2008).
- d. The environments may be less pleasant and encouraging for physical activity. This may ultimately result in poor health issues.
- e. Culture: the people's culture and worldview may have some influence. For example, Pacific peoples have strong spiritual and cultural connections with food and the ability to provide lavish amounts of food for family and visitors is important (Rush and Rusk, 2009).

It is thinkable that an adequate agricultural performance may help in contributing positively to the food security of many nations, even though, achieving food security in its entirety continues to be a challenge not only for the emerging nations but also for all countries. The difference actually lies in the magnitude of the problem in terms of its severity and proportion of the population affected. In developed nations, the problem is alleviated by providing targeted food security interventions, including food aid in the form of direct food relief, food stamps, or indirectly through subsidized food production. These efforts have significantly reduced food insecurity in some regions. Similar approaches have been employed in some developing countries but with less success. The poor results of such intervention programmes could be due to the inadequate resource base of such countries, shorter duration of intervention, or different systems most of which are intrinsically heterogeneous among other factors. The soaring complexity in a country's food insecurity experience could be due but not actually limited to several factors which may include: the lack of apparatus and methodologies for assessing the effects of long-term policies in the system, actors' (non-governmental organizations and government agencies) failures in playing appropriate roles in the system thus acting under different influences and pressure, the lack of a holistic system model to facilitate intervention and understanding of the system (Saeed, 1994). Other factors are high causality between different facets of a country such as the socio-economic, political and environmental milieu, performance of the food economy and practices related to the health sector.

The concepts of food security have evolved in the last 30 years to reflect changes in official policy thinking (Clay, 2002; Heidhues *et al.* 2004). The term first originated in the mid-1970s, when the World Food

Conference defined food security at the international and national level as a food supply that could ensure the availability and price stability of basic foodstuffs. Although there are other several definitions of food security, in most developed countries, food security can be defined as access to nutritionally adequate, safe, and personally acceptable foods and the ability to acquire them in a socially acceptable way (Parnell and Smith, 2008). The World Food Summit of 1996 defined food security as existing “when all people at all times have access to sufficient, safe, affordable and nutritious food to maintain a healthy and active life.” Usually, the concept of food security is defined as including both physical and economic access to food that meets people's dietary needs as well as their food preferences. The definition was later extended by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) to include individual- and household-level access (Clay 2002). The widely accepted World Food Summit definition reinforces the multidimensional nature of food security as including three major pillars which are: food accessibility, availability, and utilization. This definition can as well be described diagrammatically as shown in Figure 1 below with food security being at the center of availability, access, and utilization.

Fig. 1: Diagrammatic expression of food security

Even though the world has experienced an increase in the world food production in the last few decades, the global effort to meet the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) of reducing hunger by half in 2015 was beyond reach. Quite a number of countries were really on track, but achieving these targets remained a great challenge and nightmare for many others. As a matter of fact, the number of people suffering from persistent hunger has increased from about 800 million in 1996 to over one billion recently, (FAO, 2009) of which almost all the hungry people, about 780 million people live in developing nations while about 11 million people are undernourished in developed nations. In order words, between the periods of 2014-2016, one in nine of world populations were suffering from chronic undernourishment (FAO, 2014). Food security of many nations is affected by a plethora of factors which include unstable social and political environments that prevent sustainable economic growth, war and civil-strive, macroeconomic imbalances in trade, natural resource constraints, poor human resource base, gender inequality, inadequate education, poor health, the absence of good governance (most of which are prevalent in Africa, some part of Asia and Latin American countries) and natural disasters, such as floods and locust invasion, among others. All these and other factors contribute to a greater degree to either insufficient national food availability or insufficient access to food by households and individuals.

According to Raskin *et al.*, 2010, agriculture provides essential nourishment for people and is the indispensable foundation for many economic activities. As a result, sound agricultural practices and adequate nutrition are central to both human and environmental well-being. Agriculture remains the largest employment sector in most developing countries, and international agriculture agreements are fundamental to such a country's food security. It has been argued that trade liberalization may in some way reduce a country's food security by reducing agricultural employment levels, due to this concern, a group of World Trade Organization (WTO) member states recommended that negotiations on agricultural agreements should allow developing countries to re-evaluate and raise tariffs on key products to protect national food security and employment, (WTO, 2000)

Agriculture provides the livelihood for approximately 2.6 billion people (i.e., about 40% of global population). In most developing countries, agriculture accounts for between 20-60% of gross domestic product (GDP). In agriculture-based developing countries, it may generate on average, about 30% of GDP and employs almost 65% of the labor force. The industries and services linked to agriculture in value chains often account for more than 30% of GDP, even in largely urbanized countries. Out of about 5.5 billion people in developing countries, about 3 billion live in rural areas. Of these rural inhabitants, an estimated 2.5 billion are in households involved in agriculture. (World Bank, 2008 and Herren *et al.*, 2011). Despite the modern system of industrial and precision agriculture, productive as it has been in recent decades, about 1.3 billion people are still left without food and poverty-stricken, 70% of whom reside in rural areas (Ulrich, 2011).

Data and Methodology

Data used in this study were from secondary sources inclusive of a database of reputable organizations such as the United Nation's Food and Agriculture Organization (FAOSTAT) and the World Bank. The process of data collection from the databases was meticulously carried out with adequate sorting, double-checking and comparison as much as possible and applicable. Data for the periods 2003 up to 2011 were considered in the study because of the consistency in the data across several sources thereby giving credence to the reliability of such.

Five regions of the world were considered for this comparative study of agricultural performance, and these include Africa, Asia, Europe, Latin America and North America. The countries in each region were purposively selected based on their pedigree in agriculture and the availability of data on their performance indicators. Regions that are tagged "Mixed Economies" in this paper are those that have both developed and developing countries data on agricultural performance indicators used under the same region. For instance, in Asia, Japan was selected which is a developed nation while Malaysia and Saudi-Arabia are developing nations.

BRIC countries (which are made up of Brazil, Russia, India, and China) were also considered in the study in order to ascertain if the economic relationships or cooperation of these countries actually affects their level of food productivity/food security as compared to the rest of the world. More countries were purposively selected in Europe than the rest of other regions in order to compensate for the low population in that region when compared with the rest of the world.

For the purpose of this study, therefore, Table 1 contains the countries selected from each region and the list of countries that made up a BRIC community whose values were aggregated for comparative purposes. The analysis was focused on the aggregated values of the indicators, while reference is made to individual countries, where it is imperative to do so.

The percentage of the average annual rate of growth was calculated and aggregated agricultural performance indicators of these regions (such as available agricultural land, available arable land, fertilizer consumption, food production index, land under cereal production, etc.) were presented in charts and tables for comparative analysis.

Table 1: Country geographic regions and grouping

Africa (Developing Economies)	Asia (Mixed Economies)	Europe (Developed Economies)	Latin America (Developing Economies)	North America (Mixed Economies)	BRIC Countries (Mixed Economies)
Cameroon	Japan	Austria	Argentina	Canada	Brazil*
Cote d'Ivoire	Malaysia*	France	Colombia	Mexico*	Russia
Ghana	Saudi-Arabia*	Germany	Uruguay	U.S.A	India*
Nigeria		Italy			China
South Africa		Netherlands			
		Spain			
		United Kingdom			

* = *developing economies*

Discussions

Table 2 shows the population of economically (agriculture) active people in each studied region. BRIC countries show a higher percentage of active people all through the years under consideration. This might be highly connected with the population density of BRIC members such as China and India. The high percentage of active agricultural people will definitely contribute to the high level of agricultural output and high Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in each member nation and in each region at large, *ceteris paribus*. In all the regions, Africa showed a relatively low percentage of the population of economically active people. The highest recorded was in 2011 with 57.68 percent compared with Europe, Asia, North and South America and the BRICs which recorded about 66.23 percent, 65.17 percent, 66.9 percent, 64.81 percent and 69.28 percent respectively in the same year. This might be as a result of poor nutritional value and poor health care delivery in Africa coupled with a low life expectancy of average Africans which is put at between 45-55 years.

Table 2: Proportion of agriculturally active people in the regions (ages 15 - 64)

Years	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011
Region									
Africa	56.63	56.77	56.90	57.04	57.17	57.31	57.44	57.56	57.68
Europe	66.89	66.86	66.83	66.81	66.78	66.72	66.62	66.46	66.23
Asia	63.89	64.18	64.42	64.65	64.85	65.01	65.13	65.18	65.17
North America	66.08	66.30	66.49	66.66	66.79	66.89	66.96	66.96	66.90
Latin America	63.00	63.24	63.48	63.73	63.97	64.21	64.44	64.64	64.81
BRIC Countries	66.95	67.33	67.69	68.05	68.38	68.68	68.94	69.14	69.28

Source: Calculated from World Bank data, 2012.

Table 3 showed the annual rate of growth of the population of economically active people in all the regions within the specified periods. All nations of the world seem to have a kind of population control measure as revealed in table 3 below that rate of population growth in all the regions declined all through the specified periods under consideration, except for Africa and the Latin Americans whose rates of population growth were relatively steady between 2003-2009. This decline in the population of economically active people in the regions might have its consequences on the level of food production in the regions.

Table 3: Annual rate of growth of total population of economically active people in the regions

Years	2003-2006	2006-2009	2009-2011
Region			
Africa	0.18	0.17	0.11
Europe	- 0.03	- 0.07	- 0.15
Asia	0.29	0.18	0.02
North America	0.21	0.11	- 0.02
Latin America	0.28	0.28	0.14
BRIC Countries	0.41	0.32	0.13

Source: Authors' calculation based on World Bank data, 2012.

The majority of farmers are believed to be rural dwellers, hence, the higher the rural population, the higher the number of farmers in a particular country or region. Figure 2 shows that the rural population of all the regions decreased steadily across the years, even though, Africa's decrease seems to be more apparent. In Africa, the rural population decreased from 51.65 percent in 2003 to 46.63 percent in 2011. This might not be unconnected with the increasing wave of rural-urban migration in most African countries due to the poor infrastructural base in the rural areas. This factor can largely affect food security status of Africa as a region when compared with

other regions that have a deliberate decrease in population due to their country population control policies, such as China (in BRIC). Also, Asia recorded substantial rural-urban movements in the periods under review as the rural population in the region decreased to 17.96% in 2011 from 23.70% recorded in 2003. The on-going industrialization can explain this as more labor is released from the farms to work in the secondary sector.

Figure 2: Rural population (% total population) of the regions

Source: Based on World Bank data, 2012.

Figure 3 depicts that BRIC nations have more access to agricultural land than all other nations of the world. Each BRIC nation, on the average, has up to about 3,000,000sq.km agricultural land as compared to some other regions such as North America and Latin America with about 1,919,899sqkm and 647,143sqkm respectively. Europe has the smallest agricultural land followed by Africa and Asia regions, in that order. Figure 4 shows the average arable land holdings per individual in the various regions. An average farmer in Asia and Africa regions operates just about 0.08 and 0.25 hectare of arable land as compared to an average farmer from other regions of the world. The more arable land a farmer has access to, the greater the tendency of cultivating more land and producing more crops. Moreover, the greater the chance of food security of at least, in his immediate family.

Figure 3: Volume of Agricultural land (Sq.km) of the Regions

Source: Based on FAOSTAT data, 2012.

Figure 4: Available Arable Land (ha) per person in the Regions

Source: Estimated from FAOSTAT data, 2012.

Fertilizer remains a major input for the green revolution that supports food security. Fertilizer usage across the regions varies from one to another throughout the periods under consideration (2003 to 2010). Latin Americans used more fertilizer than any of the regions with about 43 percent of their total fertilizer production between 2003 to 2006 (figure 5a) and increased to about 51 percent during the period 2007-2010 (figure 5b) when compared with other region such as Africa with 12 percent of fertilizer usage between 2003 and 2006 and 14 percent in 2007-2010. BRIC and Europe have constant fertilizer use throughout the periods under consideration. In developing nations, fertilizer is used to boost the level of food production, and hence, it is assumed that the more fertilizer a nation consumes, the more the food output of the nation. Following this assumption, it can be said that Africa has a low level of food output when compared with Latin America region. Europe and North America regions are not wholly fertilizer dependants as they also engage in the use of organic fertilizer (manures) to ensure sustainable agricultural land use.

Figure 5a: Fertilizer consumption (% of fertilizer production), 2003-2006

Source: Estimates based on FAOSTAT, 2012.

Figure 5b: Fertilizer consumption (% of fertilizer production), 2007-2010

Source: Estimates based on FAOSTAT data, 2012.

If proxies with area cropped, BRIC countries lead in the production of cereals in all the regions. India and China have been the top producers among the BRIC nations; they cultivated 92,610,000 ha and 90,129,526 ha of land

under cereal cultivation in 2010, respectively. Figure 6 also shows that North America had a large expanse of land (up to about 26,827,340 ha in 2010) under cereal production. This can contribute largely to the region’s agro-based industries, the food security of the region and food exports. The graph further showed that Africa is better than other regions such as Europe, Asia, and Latin America in cereal production with about 4,288,403 ha of land in use for cereal production in 2010 alone. This might be due largely to the fact that most staple foods of people in Africa come from either cereals or their products.

Figure 6: Land under cereal production (hectares)

Source: Estimates based on FAOSTAT, 2012.

Table 4 below shows the cereal yield (kg / ha) of the regions. It can be deduced from the table that large expanse of land for cultivation of a particular crop does not automatically translate to a higher yield of that same crop. For instance (in figure 5), Africa cultivated a larger area of land for cereals than Europe, Asia, and Latin America but produced lesser yields than all the regions throughout the periods under consideration. Africa’s yield was 2,163.3kg/ha in 2010 (the most recent year in the data set) as against 6,195.1kg/ha, 5,090.8kg/ha and 4,361.1kg/ha for Europe, Asia, and Latin America, respectively. Europe has the best cereal yield among all the regions, followed by Asia, even though, they cultivated lesser land areas than North America, Africa and countries that made-up BRIC. The average annual rates of growth for cereal yield of the regions within different periods are as shown in table 5.

Table 4: Cereal yields (kg/ha) across the regions, 2003-2010

Year	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010
Region								
Africa	1737.9	1789.2	1946.4	1945.8	1750.9	2134.3	2195.5	2163.3
BRIC countries	3111.5	3138.4	3095.0	3214.3	3361.5	3609.9	3458.8	3489.2
Europe	5769.1	6630.6	6139.7	6077.8	5930.0	6561.3	6342.0	6195.1
Asia	4342.4	4644.2	4771.5	4763.0	4908.2	5027.7	4823.3	5090.8
North America	3915.9	4357.5	4266.0	4220.1	4340.8	4486.5	4654.2	4658.8
Latin America	3858.1	3991.5	4196.9	3979.9	4140.5	4006.3	3960.7	4361.1

Source: Estimates based on FAOSTAT data, 2012.

Table 5 reveals that Africa experienced growth improvements in cereal yields in 2003-2009; this declined and in fact was negative in 2009-2010. Europe’s growth was also negative (-1.19%) in 2009-2010. Latin America equally had a marginal negative growth (-0.12%) in 2006-2009. A negative rate of growth of cereals yields could be attributed to several factors inclusive of environmental (drought, flooding, pest infestation, disease infestation) and poor farm management on the farmers’ side. Improvements in agricultural extension services can alleviate the latter while strategic environmental management practices will reduce the former.

Table 5: the Average annual rate of growth of cereal yields, %.

Region	2003-2006	2006-2009	2009-2010
Africa	2.67	2.84	- 0.74
BRIC countries	0.80	1.77	0.44
Europe	1.27	1.04	- 1.19
Asia	2.21	0.31	2.63
North America	1.80	2.33	0.05
Latin America	0.77	-0.12	4.59

Source: Estimates based on FAOSTAT data, 2012.

The food production indices of the regions were estimated using the average of 2004-2006 data as a baseline. Table 6 shows that most of the regions had steady growth in food production index from 2003 to 2010 except few fluctuations in some years. Africa recorded highest production index of all the regions in 2008 and 2010 while Latin America recorded the lowest index of all the regions in 2003 but made worthwhile efforts to increase steadily throughout the period to record a creditable value of 112.61 in 2010. It is shown more clearly in table 7 through the average annual rate of growth of food production indices, the region with better performance within the periods under considerations. Latin America has the highest index between 2003-2006 and 2009-2010 followed by Africa. Europe, North America, and the BRIC nations did not perform well between the years 2009-2010 as they recorded negative values of 0.76, 0.02 and 0.09 respectively.

Table 6: Annual Food production index (2004-2006 = 100) of the Regions.

Year	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010
<i>Region</i>								
Africa	91.33	95.46	100.38	104.17	103.53	113.54	110.44	113.92
Europe	98.34	102.01	99.40	98.59	99.17	101.09	102.52	100.98
Asia	93.97	97.40	100.67	101.94	103.07	107.33	105.79	106.41
North America	93.04	98.74	99.78	101.49	102.90	106.18	106.69	106.65
Latin America	87.31	94.32	101.13	104.56	107.39	110.57	106.59	112.61
BRIC countries	93.03	96.53	99.96	103.51	110.00	111.16	112.84	112.65

Source: Estimates based on FAOSTAT, 2012.

Table 7: Average annual rate of growth of food production index

Years	2003-2006	2006-2009	2009-2010
<i>Region</i>			
Africa	3.08	1.42	1.53
Europe	0.06	0.96	-0.76
Asia	1.95	0.91	0.29
North America	2.08	1.22	-0.02
Latin America	4.12	0.48	2.67
BRIC Countries	2.53	2.07	-0.09

Source: Estimates based on FAOSTAT, 2012.

Apart from oil producing nations such as Nigeria and Cameroon, agriculture is the mainstay of the African economy. Figure 6 showed that in 2003, agriculture contributed about 27% to the Africa Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and this reduced drastically to 18% in the year 2011. From this, it can be said that Africans take agriculture as a hobby rather than a business. It could, therefore, be concluded that most of the African farmers who are aging now have no younger ones to take over from them because the latter are more interested in white collar jobs in the urban centers than farming (Takata, 2016; Fasina, 2013 and Owoyemi *et al.*, 2011). BRIC communities and Latin America had slightly steady contributions of about 12 percent to GDP in 2003 and about

10 percent in 2011. Asia has a better agricultural performance (contribution to GDP) in recent years as it rose appreciably from about 5% in 2010 to about 12% in 2011. This might be due to the deliberate efforts of the concerned nations in the Asian region to boost food production and thereby to enhance national food security. Throughout the periods under consideration, Asia, North America, and Latin America had their percentage of agriculture contribution to GDP increased (relatively), and in that order.

Figure 6: Agriculture value added (percent of GDP)

Source: *Estimates based on World Bank data, 2012.*

Conclusion

Food security issue is not just limited to a region; it is a challenge that the whole world must find a sustainable solution to. To that extent, trade policies should not antagonize realistic food exchange goals. The root cause of food insecurity in developing countries is the inability of people to gain access to food as at when due. While the rest of the world has made significant progress towards poverty alleviation, some regions of the world, Africa in particular, continue to lag behind. Many factors have contributed to this unpleasantness including poor farm technologies, civil wars, poor governance, frequent drought, and famine; climate change and environmental issues, and the high prevalence of pests and disease. Since almost all rural households in Africa depended directly or indirectly on agriculture and given the large contribution of the sector to the overall economy, one might expect agriculture to be a key component of growth and development. However, whereas agriculture-led growth played an important role in slashing poverty and transforming the economies of many Asian and Latin American countries, the same is yet to manifest in Africa.

Africa continent recorded low index values in most, if not all, the indicators discussed above. The population of agriculturally active people in the region was so low compared to all other regions because farming is not interesting to the young generations coupled with high rate of rural-urban migration by the youths to find 'white collar' jobs. This might be a major reason why the contribution of agriculture to GDP in Africa is declining year-by-year. African countries have great potentials that could support agricultural growth to transform their economies only if conditions could be met. Such include increased investments in farm technology, infrastructure, markets, as well as improved governance and government policies that provide an enabling environment. Asia and North America are doing fine as they showed significant improvements since 2010 in terms of their agricultural contribution to GDP. Even though BRIC community recorded a fair value in some of the indicators, it appears that the relationship of its members has not really affected their agricultural sector performance as one would have expected.

De Janvry observed (in 1981) that Latin American countries experienced rapid industrialization between the 1950s and 1970s and agricultural growth hardly matched rising food demand caused by an increase in population growth and urbanization. Industrial growth rose to 8% per year during 1965–73, while per capita agricultural production stagnated and even fell in some countries. As a result, food imports increased from an annual growth rate of 3.1 percent during the 1950s to more than 12 percent in the early 1970s. It was further

observed that with the rise in world prices for grains, food imports led to substantial strains on the balance of trade and the exchange rate that led to inflationary pressures. In recent time, however, Latin America has improved in agricultural performance as they recorded a better average annual rate of growth in cereal and food production indices of 4.59% and 2.67% respectively than all other regions between the years 2009-2010.

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